

Re-evaluating the role of Makerspaces as a form of incubation: Implications for Policy and Practice

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Abstract

Providing support structures for new businesses is seen within most developed economies as a policy priority and efforts in this regard have attracted considerable levels of academic interest. Various authors have tracked the evolution of different forms of incubation provider. Unfortunately, the various services provided by makerspaces has not attracted an equivalent level of academic interest within business journals. This development paper attempts to produce a comparison between makerspaces and more established models of incubation support in order to investigate similarities and differences. The methodology utilised includes a systematic literature review and an open-access database made up of data on makerspaces operating within the United Kingdom. The theoretical lens of model design is also utilised to identify key elements. The paper identifies considerable over-lap between makerspaces and more established models of incubation support. Policy implications are referred to as well as issues for practitioners.

Keywords

Makerspace, Entrepreneurs, Incubation

1 Introduction

Extant literature on Makerspaces is located in several domains: articles can be found in journals devoted to library studies (de Boer, 2015) or to education (Kjällander, 2018) both of which reflect the presence and activities of Makerspaces, but within the literature devoted to business relatively little has been published. The opening premise from which this article proceeds is the following: Makerspaces, as a form of incubation, have not received sufficient consideration within academic literature devoted to the growth of businesses. A preparatory literature review discovered an example of a paper which encapsulates the current viewpoint towards makerspaces in the business literature. When *Technovation*, a leading academic journal devoted to technology and innovation, published a systematic review of the literature on technology-based incubation in 2016, its authors (Mian, Lamine and Fayolle, 2016) operationalised incubation to include the following types of institutional support: science parks, technology incubators, innovation centres and accelerators. Makerspaces were not specifically included. This article will review existing models of incubation support and deconstruct them in order to ascertain the extent to which the activities undertaken by makerspaces resemble and mirror those within more established forms of incubation. This article begins by tracing the development of incubation services at a general level and then focuses on the development path of makerspaces.

The establishment of a dynamic and prospering small enterprise sector is seen by policyholders as essential for the economic development of countries (Audretsch, 2002). Consistent evidence from many developed economies, does however, point to the many practical obstacles and challenges facing nascent entrepreneurs and their fledgling businesses. An extremely high level of business failure is unfortunately a characteristic of this sector and numerous authors have pointed to the need for aspiring entrepreneurs

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to be given greater access to resources during the crucial early stages of their ventures in order to overcome these obstacles (Belso-Martinez, Molina-Morales, & Mas-Verdu, 2013; Honjo, 2000). In response to this need, various forms of incubation services have been made available to businesses (Bruneels, 2012). Some of the earliest initiatives were seen in the creation of the Stanford Research Park, California, established in 1951 and the Industrial Center of Batavia, New York, an incubator established in 1959. Globally, there are currently in excess of 7,000 incubator programs worldwide, one third of which are technology-oriented (Joshi and Apoorva, 2015, referring to NBIA data).

Bruneels (2012) traces the evolution of incubators from the 1980s when they first became commonplace in western economies. The first phase of incubators were typified as having the predominant aim of providing office space as a means of assisting agglomeration (Adkins, 2002). At around this time there was also seen the expansion of Science Parks (Smith and Zhang, 2012). According to Bruneels (2012), it was not until the 1990s that there was a widespread expansion of services away from purely one of accommodation to include intangible services in the form of in-house business support services. Additionally, it was also during this period that incubation services oriented towards assisting technology-based start-ups became more prevalent. Bruneels (2012) categorises these as a third generation of incubator. More recently, Pauwels *et al* (2016) identifies accelerators, in which the incubated firm will participate in a relatively short-term (typically thirteen weeks), boot-camp type environment aimed at rapid maturation of the business, as a new form of incubation system. Additionally, other forms of incubator, such as the virtual incubators (Nowack and Grantham, 2000) which do not have a physical location have also emerged over the past ten or so years.

2 Methodology

Since the objective of this article is to compare makerspaces with other forms of incubation, existing archetypes of incubation are identified. They are treated as the unit of analysis. In order to ascertain the types of entity in existence which provide these services a systematic literature review was carried out using a protocol and following best practice (Tranfield et al, 2003). This included the creation of specific search terms, the identification of relevant journal articles where the dominant theme included examination of forms of incubation and the removal of irrelevant or insignificant literature. Additionally, relevant websites of key stakeholders such as governmental departments – both national and regional – were also checked. Finally, data drawn from an open dataset (NESTA, 2016) compiled on behalf of a British innovation charity, NESTA during 2014- 2015 were examined. The data, based on a survey, interviews and desk-research, sets out information on 97 makerspaces operating within the United Kingdom. The identified data was analysed using a multiple case-study process (Eisenhardt 1989) of cross-case analysis in which dimensions and categories are initially identified followed by a process of identifying similarities and differences at the inter-case level.

The second stage of the analysis was to employ the design perspective proposed by Zott and Amit (2010) as a theoretical lens for identifying the primary design parameters of the different forms of incubation provider: this approach was adopted, in a similar manner by Pauwels et al (2016) to analyse accelerators; for this article, it was applied on a wider basis to compare makerspaces with other forms of incubation. In recent years the study of business model innovation has attracted considerable amounts of academic interest. Business models are seen as a form of architecture (Dubosson-Torbay, Osterwalder, & Pigneur) which can be used as a means of explaining the manner in which value is created and captured at an organisational level (Amit and Zott, 2001). Accordingly, business models are seen as embracing the range of activities undertaken by the entity, in a holistic manner, which is depicted as the “heuristic logic” (Chesbrough and Rosenbloom, 2002 p.529) of the entity. Using a business model perspective is particularly appropriate for examining incubation providers since it allows us to identify common themes that are orchestrated across a range of business models. Zott and Amit (2010) advocate that in analysing business models it is necessary to focus on the design elements which represent the activity system.

3 Findings and analysis

The data was grouped into four categories to provide distinct elements which are common among existing models of incubation. The four categories are: (1) Activities and resources; (2) Place and duration; (3) Control and governance, and (4) Membership. Each will be considered in turn.

Activities and resources

A wide range of services are offered through incubation. Traditional models of incubation focussed on traditional business support services and progressed to offer more intangible services such as general business advisory services (Mian, 1996). It is also the case that business support may embrace other forms of support (Mian, 1996; Aernoudt, 2004: 127). Incubators also have an intermediary role in connecting incubatees to other organizations through their external network (Bergek and Norrman, 2008: 24-5).

As incubation services have become more specialised, especially in the context of University-focussed incubators and Science Parks, the diffusion of specialised knowledge as well as technical support have become more prevalent (Bruneels et al., 2012: 111). The availability of support services varies: science parks typically do not provide extensive support services in the same way that conventional incubators might (NESTA, 2008). Another important area of resourcing provided by incubation providers is access to the benefits of networks (Schwartz and Hornych, 2010). The value of networks comes in the form of access to knowledge and to connections to parties who would otherwise not be connected. Other services which are offered by incubation providers which are designed to assist tenants include activities designed to enhance social capital: this is a core activity for all incubation providers. The provision of technical lab equipment is another core activity (Crittenden & Woodside, 2006; Mian, 1996). Alongside the provision of services such as access to laboratory equipment, more specialised legal advisory services connected with not only intellectual property but also relating to connected matters such as patenting and licensing agreements have become more prevalent.

The NESTA data and a literature review suggests that makerspaces offer an equally wide range of services but there is great diversity in terms of the types offered. Within the UK, NESTA reported that the majority of makerspaces were community based within specific geographic locations. Makerspaces have been found to be embedded within these communities with strong linkages to local schools and libraries. Within the user groups of makerspaces there is growing evidence that they constitute a place where considerable social interaction and networking takes place. Much of the there was considerable evidence that members shared knowledge openly, frequently and unconditionally. Networking with government at a local and regional level was widespread.

Advisory services offered by makerspaces have an emphasis towards the provision of technical support services: these will often take the form of technicians assisting users to operate specialist machinery. In terms of more mainstream advisory services, such as guidance on business creation or on the production of business plans, is less frequently offered. However, a particular area of business support which is of specific benefit to nascent entrepreneurs, is the assistance offered by makerspaces in the production of prototypes. Birtchnell et (2017) report on the Berlin FabLab where 80% of SMES use their facilities for rapid prototyping.

In the case of equipment, according to the NESTA data based on activities within British makerspaces, approximately two-thirds of them offered more than five types of tools. Additionally, digital and manual tools were commonly available. Equipment designed to facilitate digital fabrication was found in 73 per cent of the makerspaces; general tools were found in 60 per cent, general hand tools and electronics at 60 per cent and woodwork at 52 per cent. Computer equipment was found in about half of the locations. Equipment designed to facilitate more specialised work such as photography or printmaking, ceramics and sculpture were found in a smaller number of makerspaces. In one makerspace highly specialised equipment for biotech were found in a facility based in Manchester. Makerspaces, in the majority of cases, also offered a broad range of educational services: these were found to include inductions into using specific forms of tool but a wide range of educational courses were also available in more than 90 per cent

of cases. School out-reach programmes were widespread with some 24 offering specialised educational programmes to Schools. Tools and equipment aren't the only things that denote a makerspace.

3.1 Place and duration

Incubation activities are performed at a wide range of physical locations and the space and the amount of space occupied by the incubated firm can vary enormously: tenants of science parks may occupy substantial areas with little or very limited common spaces with other tenants. On the other hand, tenants of incubators who occupy shared workspaces are unlikely to occupy areas of spaces which are exclusive to themselves. Common elements among incubation facilities include shared space and the opportunity to work alongside other parties facing similar challenges (Hackett and Dilts, 2004: 57; Bruneel et al., 2012: 110). More recently, virtual incubators have been created which operate without specific physical locations (Nowack, 2000). Makerspaces share the same level of diversity as other forms of incubation. In some situations, especially where there is hybrid governance, such as in libraries under local government ownership, or universities, the location will be co-located within the parent organisation (de Boer, 2015). The NESTA data for UK makerspaces showed a wide range of diversity in types of location including mobile or temporary facilities. The actual size of the makerspaces also varied enormously with an average space of 209 square metres.

A reduction in the time necessary to grow a business is a key objective of incubation (Clarysse et al., 2005). The period in which a firm engages with incubation services varies considerably. In the case of advanced technological businesses located within highly specialised bio-technology incubators of the kind described by Baraldi and Ingemans (2016) the stated period is up to fifteen years. In other situations, an incubation period of between three and five years is more typical (Mian, 1997: 281; Bergek and Norman, 2008). In the case of accelerators, the time period is often considerably shorter. According to Hochberg (2015), the normal period of occupancy within an accelerator is thirteen weeks. Makerspaces do not limit their services to specific periods: membership is normally on a subscription basis and it will endure indefinitely subject to payment of membership dues.

3.2 Control and governance

Incubation providers are frequently collaborations between universities, industry and government (Etzkowitz, 2002). They have a wide range of organizational forms: in cases where the funding is provided by an established organization such as a university or library, control may be vested in the parent organization. In other cases, governance will be more autonomous, especially where the incubation provider is organized as a commercial venture. Over the past ten or so years there has been a sizeable increase in business models for incubation providers where revenues will be generated from for-profit activities. Among such forms of incubation, the provider cannot rely on public support to cover all of the costs associated with the provision of incubation services. Accordingly, it is necessary for revenue to be generated from commercial activities. University sponsored incubators often profit from spin-offs where profit can be generated from the shareholding held in sold-off incubated businesses (Clarysse et al, 2005) or from income generated from technology transfer activities from the exploitation of intellectual property created by incubated businesses. In another example of this profit-oriented model, accelerators will commonly require a small share-ownership to be granted to them at the outset of the program by all participants. With increased profit-orientation comes more focus on timelines for exits and performativity. In the case of science-based Incubators, such as the example of the Karolinska Institute put forward by Baraldi and Ingemans (2016), the incubated business will remain typically for between ten and fifteen years. Equally, in the case of accelerators the timeline is limited to thirteen weeks at the culmination of which the incubated firm will pitch for investment support from potential investors.

Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens (2012) point to the types of monitoring that can occur in incubators: goal setting, agreement to specific business plans and budget setting, and the appointment of directors and senior management. These forms of monitoring and control are by no means ubiquitous but they have been increasingly common, especially in cases where the incubation system is profit-oriented. It is still the case, especially in incubation environments of a more generic nature, where specialisation in technology is not the dominant objective, and where the services offered are also more generic and more property-based, the level of control over incubatees is less restrictive and limited in extent.

Makerspaces within the United Kingdom were found to be overwhelmingly self-organised structures run by volunteers. The dominant form of income was from subscriptions or from fee income from providing use of tools and equipment. Governance within makerspaces is over-whelmingly self-organising: not-for-profit structures are ubiquitous and a communal attitude to the management of the shared space is normal.

Membership

Gaining access to incubation services will typically require incubated firms to make an application for membership and the criteria for admission will vary in complexity. Access to an incubation support system in the form of accelerator programs appears to be among the most challenging to enter. Given that large numbers of applicants will often apply to join these programs, especially those run by the most prestigious (such as Y Combinator, 500 Startups and Techstars), it is normal for exhaustive background checks of the applicants and a very thorough-going review of the business idea to be undertaken (Hochberg, 2015). Very few applicants gain acceptance. Hackett and Dilts (2004) point to the fact that most incubators will give emphasis to either the qualities of the applicant or the idea itself which will determine entry to incubation services. In cases such as entry to Science Parks it will also require specific levels of technical specialisation as well (Smith and Zhang, 2012). Makerspaces are, however, open-access in the sense that screening of potential members or of their ideas is undertaken prior to acceptance by the granting of membership. The NESTA data demonstrates that UK makerspaces vary in size from small community based projects to larger facilities with more than a thousand members (in five per cent of case. One quarter of makerspaces did not require membership in order to access the facility.

4 Conclusions

The range of activities offered by incubation providers is vast and the creation of archetypes as a means of evaluating particular forms of incubation is subject to limitation. For example, the preceding discussion illustrated that even within well-known forms of incubation, such as incubators, there is considerable diversity. The types of services offered by a technology-based incubator of the kind described by Baraldi (2016) in operation at the Karolinska Institute is more specialised and extensive in terms of the services offered: highly specialised scientific equipment and expert specialists will be present, not only to offer technical, scientific assistance but also specialists who can assist in areas such as intellectual property rights. On the other hand, more generic incubators will give greater emphasis to generic assistance in terms of restricting their assistance to less specialised areas of activity. In the same way, the services offered by makerspaces are also variable in their scale of operations. Some makerspaces operating in the UK, such as those profiled in the NESTA database, offer very specialised and highly technical assistance. This is seen in the case of the MadFabLab, situated in Manchester in the north of England, which is a makerspace which provides a bio-lab of the highest quality to its users. In other cases, a makerspace can be far more modest in its offerings: sometimes it may be limited to the provision of generic hand-tools and supporting technical assistance.

Subject to this limitation, it is possible to make the following observation about the role played by makerspaces as an incubation support service to businesses. There are several apparent strengths in the makerspace model. The first is its emphasis on inclusivity which appears to be far wider than that offered by other forms of incubation. For example, the NESTA data showed that about one quarter of incubators do not have any membership requirement and the remaining ones do not generally screen prospective users extensively. In the case of other forms of incubation, particularly some of the more recent models, such as accelerators, there is extensive screening both in terms of the perceived suitability of the applicant and of the business idea prior to entry being granted. The implication of the more inclusive approach is that more prospective entrepreneurs, especially those constrained by lack of access to resources, will be more likely to utilise makerspaces. A considerable benefit flowing from this is that prospective entrepreneurs will be able also organise proto-typing and product development within an environment where access is more readily granted. Through the development of viable proto-types, the nascent entrepreneur is also likely to gain an enhanced sense of self-efficacy in the sense that they will feel that

their business idea is potentially more viable if the entrepreneurial vision can be translated into a workable example. Going forward, this brief paper identifies some tangible strengths within the makerspace movement which are capable of offering assistance to fledgling businesses. Fundamentally, their role as nurturers of nascent business ideas, especially where proto-typing takes place, together with the impact on entrepreneurs of enhanced self-efficacy as a consequence of gaining access to such services, does not appear to have received adequate research within business literature. The same is true about the impact of the networks offered by makerspaces on regional development. It appears – certainly within the UK, but also in other countries, that link

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